

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF SOME ADAMANTYL-CONTAINING HYDRAZONES

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ABSTRACT

Several adamantyl-containing quaternary salts of benzyliidenehydrazinylpyridine, based on benzyl, ethylphenyl, and propylphenyl groups on the pyridinium nitrogen, were synthesized and tested for potential antibacterial and antifungal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* using a microdilution method. Results of antimicrobial testing showed that compounds containing the 3-phenylpropyl chain exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, and compound 3d was the most active in the series against all bacterial and fungal strains tested.

Keywords: hydrazones, pyridinium salts, adamantyl, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The shortage of new antibacterial drugs due to growing bacterial resistance to antimicrobial agents is a major challenge in the development of new drugs. Quaternary amine derivatives have previously been reported to exhibit antimicrobial properties [1–4]. Certain mono- and bis-quaternary ammonium compounds, including various alkyl chain lengths with various hydrophobic substituents, have been found to exhibit antimicrobial activity [5–7].

Pyridinium halides, like quaternary nitrogen salts, exhibit antimicrobial properties and adsorption properties on negatively charged solids. The antimicrobial activity of 1-alkylpyridinium salts depends on their adsorption activity on the surface of bacterial cells [8–16] and the pKa values of the corresponding pyridines [17]. The factors that control their antimicrobial activity are molecular hydrophobicity [18,19], adsorbability [20], surface activity [19] and electron density [21,22] of the quaternary nitrogen atom.

These compounds have one hydrophobic alkyl chain and one hydrophilic quaternary nitrogen ion group in one molecule, which provides greater surface activity and more pronounced antimicrobial activity compared to conventional antimicrobial agents [23].

On the other hand, Schiff bases are important in medicine, and their biological activities have been reported in many studies [24,25]. Hydrazones, a special group of Schiff bases, are also known as one of the most important classes of organic compounds, some of which exhibit significant biological activities such as antimicrobial [26–30], antituberculosis [31–33], anticancer [34–36], analgesic [37], anti-inflammatory [37], antiplatelet [38], and antiviral [39, 40] activities. The data reported in these studies showed that the side chain attached to the pyridinium nitrogen significantly affected the antimicrobial activity. Among them, compounds with 3-phenylpropyl chains showed remarkable activity [40].

Based on these results, ortho-methyl, -methoxyl, -hydroxyl benzyliidenehydrazinylpyridinium salts with benzyl, 2,6-dichlorobenzyl, 2-phenylethyl, and 3-phenylpropyl groups on the pyridine nitrogen were prepared to study the effect of such structural modifications of quaternary pyridinium salts on the expected antimicrobial activity.

In addition to the above, the objective of this study was to introduce a bulky hydrocarbon radical, adamantane, into the Schiff base molecules. The latter is widely known to enhance the lipophilicity of the drug substance, which prolongs its therapeutic effect.

Results and Discussion

Chemistry

Benzyliidenehydrazinylpyridinium salts were prepared in three steps according to the reported procedure [41] as shown in Scheme 1. In the first step, 4-chloropyridine was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in 1-propanol to give 4-hydrazinylpyridine (1). This compound was then condensed with 4-(1-adamantyl)benzaldehyde (2) in ethanol at room temperature to give hydrazone (3). In the last step, the final compounds (4a–d) were obtained by quaternization of hydrazone derivatives (3) with the appropriate substituted alkyl halides in ethanol under reflux. All the key compounds are new. Except for compounds (3) and (4), compounds (1) and (2) were previously described [42,43].

The structures of the final compounds were determined by spectral methods. The IR spectra of the final compounds showed intense absorption bands in the range of 3315–3446 cm⁻¹ and the range of 1436–1644 cm⁻¹, which were assigned to vibrations of the NH and C=N functions, respectively. In the 1H NMR spectra, the signals of the NH group protons were recorded in the range of 12.26–13.00 ppm. The signals of the protons belonging to the N=CH group were observed as singlets in the range of 8.52–8.65 ppm. The IR and 1H NMR data confirmed the condensation between the

amino and carbonyl groups. As expected, while the pyridine hydrogens at positions 2 and 6 of compound (3) showed peaks in the 8.19–8.21 ppm range, the signals of the hydrogens at these positions were in the final compounds (4a–d) in the 8.30–8.55 ppm range [44]. The shifts of these peaks to higher frequency indicated

that compounds (4) were quaternized with an alkyl halide. All ^{13}C NMR results supported the proposed structures as stated in the experimental section. The mass spectra of the final compounds (4a–d) showed molecular ion peaks that were consistent with the proposed structures.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the title compounds

Antimicrobial Activity

A series of benzylidenehydrazinylpyridinium salts with an adamantyl substituent at the para-position of the benzene ring were evaluated for antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and fungi. The bacterial strains represented important Gram-positive and Gram-negative species, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Their antibacterial activity was assessed by measuring the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) using a standard broth dilution assay (Table 1).

Based on the antimicrobial activity results, all compounds exhibited high antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and low antimicrobial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Among the

tested compounds, 4d was the most active derivative against *Staphylococcus aureus*, being as effective against this microorganism as the standard compound ceftazidime. The results showed that the longer the side chain of a compound, the greater its antimicrobial activity. In the series of adamantyl-substituted phenylpropyl derivatives, the antimicrobial activity of 4d was followed by 4c, 4a, and 4b, respectively. No significant difference in the antibacterial activity of compounds 4c and 4a was observed. Both compounds had identical MIC values against the test microorganisms, with the exception of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. According to the MIC values of the compounds, 4d had the lowest MIC values (4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) compared to other pyridinium salts.

Table 1.

Compound No	Antimicrobial activity of compounds 4a-d.			
	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
4a	35 >2048	512	20	66
4b	66	>2048	67	1030
4c	131	512	32	66
4d	<0.125 (0.06-0.5)*	1030	4	66
Ceftazidime		1 (1-4)*	4 (4-16)*	
Fluconazole		–	–	(0.25–1.0)*

* Acceptable quality control ranges of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) for strains [45,46].

This bioisosteric substitution resulted in a slight increase in antimicrobial activity. On the other hand, compounds with a 2,6-dichlorobenzyl side chain on the pyridinium nitrogen showed no activity against Gram-negative bacteria. Our study showed that all compounds exhibited stronger antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria compared to Gram-negative bacteria.

These data suggest that pyridinium salts act on cell membranes, and the surface activity of these compounds may be primarily responsible for their antibacterial properties. However, all tested compounds exhibited low antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. The weaker antifungal activity compared to the antibacterial effect may be due to differences in the compounds' mechanisms of action in inhibiting the fungal cell respiration system, rather than cell wall destruction.

Materials and methods

The melting points (mp) of the synthesized compounds were recorded on a Boetius bench. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM300 spectrometer (300 and 75 MHz, respectively) in DMSO- d_6 and CDCl_3 at 25 °C. Chemical shifts were measured in DMSO- d_6 with TMS as an internal standard. IR spectra were recorded using the thin film method and in KBr tablets on a Bruker Alpha spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectra were measured on an Agilent 1100 LC/MSD instrument. Reagents and solvents used for the synthesis were purchased from Aldrich. 4-(1-Adamantyl)benzaldehyde was provided by AKos GmbH. Thin-layer chromatography was performed on silica gel-coated 60 F254 plates (Merck). The spots were developed using UV light or iodine.

Synthesis of 4-Hydrazinopyridine Hydrochloride (1).

Compound (1) was prepared according to the method described in [47]. A solution of 4-chloropyridine (0.01 mol) and hydrazine monohydrate (0.15 mol) in 1-propanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 18 h. The solution was cooled to 0 °C, the precipitate was filtered off, washed with cold 1-propanol, and crystallized from ethanol. M.p. 242–243 °C (ref. [47,48], 242–243 °C).

4-(2-(4-(1-Adamantyl)benzylidene)hydrazinyl)pyridine (3).

4-Hydrazinylpyridine (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde derivative (2) (0.01 mol) were stirred in ethanol (30 ml) at room temperature for 4–9 h. The precipitate

was filtered off, washed with cold ethanol, and crystallized from ethanol. Yield 73%. M.p. 232 °C. IR (v, cm^{-1}): 1427, 1452, 1486, 1527, 1538 (Ar-C=C and N=C), 2886, 2948 (aliphatic C-H), 3014 (Ar-C-H), 3210 (N-H); ^1H NMR (δ , ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 6.97 (2H, d, J = 6.2 Hz, Py-H), 7.23 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.19 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.21 (2H, d, J = 6.2 Hz, Py-H), 10.80 (1H, s, NH).

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds (4a-d).

Hydrazone (3) (0.01 mol) and the corresponding alkyl halide (0.02 mol) were refluxed in ethanol (30 mL) for 10–40 h. The mixture was cooled to 0 °C, and the resulting precipitate was filtered and washed with cold ethanol. The crude products were crystallized from ethanol, yielding compounds (4a-d).

1-Benzyl-4-(2-(4-(1-adamantyl)benzylidene)hydrazinyl)pyridine chloride (4a). Yield 68%. M.p. 267 °C. IR (v, cm^{-1}): 1455, 1482, 1517, 1544, 1600, (Ar-C=C and N=C), 1644 (N⁺=C), 2838, 2911, 2979 (aliphatic C-H), 3037 (Ar-C-H), 3397 (N-H). ^1H -NMR (δ , ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 5.48 (2H, s, N⁺-CH₂-Ph), 7.16 (1H, dd, J = 7.0, 2.3 Hz, Py-H), 7.23 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.36–7.42 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.56 (1H, d, J = 7.4 Hz, Py-H), 8.47 (1H, d, J = 7.4 Hz, Py-H), 8.55 (1H, d, J = 7.4 Hz, Py-H), 8.62 (1H, s, N=CH), 13.00 (1H, s, NH). ^{13}C NMR (δ , ppm): 60.75 107.80, 109.64, 126.96, 127.47, 128.78, 129.46, 129.78, 130.9, 131.7, 132.18, 136.20, 137.92, 143.72, 144.89, 147.99, 154.38. MS (m/z): 458 (M⁺), 91.135, 77.

1-(2,6-Dichlorobenzyl)-4-(4-(1-adamantyl)benzylidene)hydrazinyl)pyridinium chloride (4b).

Yield 72%. M.p. 298 °C; IR (v, cm^{-1}): 1436, 1513, 1581 (Ar-C=C and N=C), 1644 (N⁺=C), 2694, 2886 (aliphatic C-H), 3052 (Ar-C-H), 3442 (N-H). ^1H NMR (δ , ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 5.70 (2H, s, N⁺-CH₂-Ph), 7.14 (1H, dd, J = 7.2, 2.8 Hz, Py-H), 7.26–7.30 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.34 (1H, td, J = 7.4, 1.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.52–7.56 (2H, m, Py-H), 7.23 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, dd, J = 7.0, 1.6 Hz, Py-H), 8.34 (1H, dd, J = 7.2, 1.6 Hz, Py-H), 8.60 (1H, s, N=CH), 13.00 (1H, s, NH). ^{13}C -NMR (δ , ppm): 56.44, 108.29, 110.28, 125.29, 128.30, 129.22, 129.72, 130.00, 131.74, 133.16, 134.16, 137.00, 143.50, 144.66, 144.74, 148.69, 154.80. MS (m/z): 527 (M⁺), 135, 159, 145.

4-(4-(1-Adamantyl)benzylidene)hydrazinyl)-1-phenethylpyridinium bromide (4c). Yield 87%. M.p.190 °C. IR (v, cm⁻¹): 1455, 1513, 1546, 1577 (Ar-C=C and N=C), 1644 (N⁺=C), 2836, 2908 (aliphatic C-H), 3054 (Ar-C-H), 3415 (N-H); ¹H NMR (δ, ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 3.13 (2H, t, J = 7.2 Hz, N⁺-CH₂-CH₂-Ph), 4.50 (2H, t, J = 7.2 Hz, N⁺-CH₂-CH₂-Ph), 7.03 (1H, dd, J = 7.0, 2.3 Hz, Py-H), 7.19-7.36 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.23 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.50 (1H, dd, J = 7.0, 2.3 Hz, Py-H), 8.30 (1H, d, J = 7.4 Hz, Py-H), 8.35 (1H, d, J = 7.0 Hz, Py-H), 8.53 (1H, s, N=CH), 12.38 (1H, s, NH). ¹³C NMR (δ, ppm): 36.92, 59.03, 107.37, 108.99, 126.94, 127.36, 127.55, 129.23, 129.62, 130.96, 131.73, 132.12, 137.33, 137.89, 143.71, 144.84, 147.53, 154.10. MS (m/z): 513(M⁺), 77, 91, 135.

4-(4-(1-Adamantyl)benzylidene)hydrazinyl)-1-(3-phenylpropyl)pyridinium bromide (4d). Yield 49%. M.p.160 °C; IR (v, cm⁻¹): 1454, 1488, 1511, 1552, 1585, (Ar-C=C and N=C), 1644 (N⁺=C), 2827, 2915 (aliphatic C-H), 3058 (Ar-C-H), 3424 (N-H); ¹H NMR (δ, ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 2.12 (2H, quin, J = 7.6 Hz, N⁺-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-Ph), 2.60 (2H, t, J = 7.8 Hz, N⁺-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-Ph), 4.28 (2H, t, J = 7.2 Hz, N⁺-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-Ph), 7.06 (1H, dd, J = 7.2, 2.4 Hz, Py-H), 7.16-7.30 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.756 (1H, dd, J = 6.8, 2.4 Hz, Py-H), 7.23 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H), 7.83 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, Ar-H) 8.39 (1H, d, J = 6.8 Hz, Py-H), 8.46 (1H, d, J = 7.2 Hz, Py-H), 8.52 (1H, s, N=CH), 12.34 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (δ, ppm): 32.28, 52.50, 58.08, 107.50, 109.15, 126.76, 126.98, 127.50, 128.89, 129.12, 131.00, 131.80, 132.14, 137.33, 141.15, 143.79, 144.80, 147.64, 154.29. MS(m/z): 527 (M⁺), 77, 91, 135.

Antimicrobial activity

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by broth microdilution according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) [45,46]. The in vitro antimicrobial activity of the final compounds (4a-d) was assessed against standard strains: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, and *Candida albicans* ATCC 90028. Antibacterial and antifungal assays were performed in Mueller-Hinton broth and Sabouraud dextrose broth, respectively. All synthesized compounds were weighed (10 mg), dissolved in DMSO (250 μL), and diluted with water (750 μL) to prepare stock solutions of 10 mg/mL. Serial dilutions from 2048 to 1 μg/mL were performed in a 96-well plate. Fifty μL of bacterial suspension obtained from a 24-hour culture (~106 CFU/mL) was added to each well with a final DMSO concentration of 1:16. The plates were incubated at 35°C for 24 hours. We tested Ceftazidime as an antimicrobial agent for quality control of the method. Each experiment was repeated twice.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we described the synthesis of a series of adamantyl-containing benzylidenehydrazinylpyridinium salts (4a-d) with antimicrobial activity. The final synthesized compounds were characterized by spectral data (IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, MS). Both the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of the final

compounds (4a-d) were reported for the first time. Compounds (4a-d) were found to possess moderate activity against *S. aureus*. Notable activity was observed for compounds bearing a 3-phenylpropyl side chain on the nitrogen atom. The most active compound was 4-(4-(1-adamantylbenzylidene)hydrazinyl)-1-(3-phenylpropyl)pyridinium bromide (4d), with an MIC of 4 μg/mL against *S. aureus*. Results showed that a longer side chain on the pyridinium nitrogen resulted in increased activity.

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